

Study of Heat Transfer in a Latent Heat Storage System using Salt Hydrates for Domestic Heating Applications

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ABSTRACT

Thermal energy storage (TES) consist a technology that can be used to decrease the energy demand of buildings. It is critical for renewable energy sources (RES) applications implementation such as solar or geothermal energy, as it provides a mean to store the excess energy produced. TES can be classified into sensible, latent heat and thermo-chemical storage. Latent heat thermal energy storage (LHTES) is the most promising due to its ability to store energy at nearly constant temperature corresponding to the phase transition temperature of the material. LHTES comprises at least a suitable phase change material (PCM) with its melting point in the desired temperature range, an adequate heat exchanger, and a container compatible with the PCM. The PCM choice for LHTES lies on the target application as the materials exhibits different characteristic properties. PCMs are classified as different groups depending on the material nature, however, in real applications the most PCMs used are paraffins (organics), salt hydrates (inorganic) and fatty acids (organics) [1-7]. Salt hydrates have high energy storage density, low price, relatively good thermal conductivity and compatibility with plastics. However, they suffer from incongruent melting and super-cooling, which can be tackled in different ways e.g by adding thickening agents. Since one of the main drawbacks of PCMs is their low thermal conductivity to fully exploit their potential in practical applications, a suitable heat exchanger is one of the key issues to be addressed. In a recent work [8] a detailed analysis of different heat exchanger configurations was carried out through experimental characterization, during both charging and discharging phases, employing a commercial PCM, RT35. Among them, the most effective from the heat transfer efficiency, resulted the compact HEX (staggered type) with PCM between coil and fins.

In the present work, the initial assessment of the working performance of a laboratory-scale LHTES unit when salt hydrates are used as PCM material is attempted. Tests were carried out in a testing rig specifically developed for such experiments using a staggered finned heat exchanger. The melting and solidification behavior of a commercial salt hydrate was studied. The operation temperatures were monitored collecting data based on the requirements of solar thermal energy storage for domestic applications. Results were used to understand the process duration and the effect of the heat transfer fluid (HTF) flow rate in both melting and solidification processes

INTRODUCTION

Due to the continuous increase in energy consumption and the respective depletion of energy resources it is necessary to develop technologies that will reduce the energy demand and increase the energy supply while utilizing renewable energy effectively. Thermal energy storage is a technology that can increase the efficiency of energy consumption particularly by bridging the period between periods when energy is harvested and periods when it is needed [1-5]. TES comprises thermochemical storage, sensible heat storage and latent heat storage, or a combination of these storage systems [1,2]. Phase change materials (PCMs) are used for latent heat storage, as they can storage and release energy by melting and solidification, thus solving the contradiction of supply and demand of energy, such as peak difference of power load and

gap of solar energy [6-7]. PCMs are divided into two main categories: organic and inorganic [4]. Organic materials can be further classified into paraffin and non paraffins such as alcohols, esters, fatty acids and glycols. Inorganic materials are subdivided into salt hydrates and metallics [1-7]. The PCM selection for a specific application depends on many criteria, including material aspects [8], the storage duration, cost, supply and utilization temperature requirements, and storage capacity. For example compatibility issues of some organic PCMs with tank container or encapsulation polymer material may exist as we recently reported [8]. Among PCM materials, salt hydrates are attractive to use due to their high energy storage density, their price and their relatively good thermal conductivity and high volumetric energy storage density [6,11]. However, they suffer from defects as supercooling, phase separation and difficulties to melt incongruently [6]. To overcome supercooling one of the most effective ways is adding nucleating agents as graphite nanoparticles, metal nanoparticles, nano-silica molecules [6, 11]. Adding thickener agents into salt hydrates is one of common methods to minimize or avoid phase separation [6, 11-13].

Various works have been conducted using PCMs in Latent heat thermal energy storage applications (LHTES) studying their thermal behavior and showing the advantages and thermal storage improvements using experimental or/and numerical approach [14-20]. Numerous configurations have been studied including different types of heat exchangers and fin configurations have been suggested as they proved to significantly enhance the heat transfer during the phase change process [9, 14-20]. Banaszek et al [14] studied the behaviour of PCMs during charging and discharging periods in a spiral TES system. Zhang and Faghri [15] studied the heat transfer enhancement in the latent heat thermal energy storage heat exchanger using an internally finned tube. Khan et al [16] built a novel shell and tube LHS unit that they tested for different inlet temperatures and HTF flow rates. The inclusion of longitudinal fins made conduction more important than natural convection. Youssef et al [17] proposed a heat exchanger designed with spiral-wired tubes containing an organic paraffin. They carried out a CFD modelling which they validated experimentally. The model was used to study the effect of varying HTF inlet temperature and flow rate on melting and solidification processes. Liu and Groulx [18] experimentally studied heat transfer inside a horizontal copper double pipe heat exchanger with longitudinal fins. The effectiveness for heat transfer enhancement was tested and compared for two configurations: straight and angled fins. The influence of HTF inlet temperature and flow rate on melting and solidification processes were studied as well. Results showed that melting time is more strongly affected by the first parameter than by the latter. Medrano et al [9] compared different types of heat exchangers operating with RT35 by Rubitherm GmbH as PCM and water as HTF. Performance evaluation was based on the required time to fully melt a certain PCM quantity with different types of heat exchangers. Results indicate that compact tube finned (staggered) heat exchanger made of aluminum fins and copper tubes widely used as evaporator or condenser in small air conditioning units, shows the highest ratio of heat transfer area to external volume. Porteiro et al [19] tested three different PCMs, two of them were hydrated salts (an encapsulated and a micro-encapsulated type) and a vegetable-based PCM was also studied with transition temperatures between 50 and 60 °C. A temperature recovery was observed after exposing the test tank to an energy demand.

In a recent work of ours [20,21], an LHTES rig has been developed in order to generate data about the performance of heat exchangers when they are used in such applications. A range of operation temperatures was monitored collecting data by four types of PCMs based on the requirements of solar thermal energy storage for residential building applications. The testing temperature range was 30-70°C and the PCMs nominal melting points used were 40-53°C. The main target of this work was to make an initial assessment of the working performance of the latter thermal energy storage (TES) unit, when using salt hydrate as PCM and in a temperature range suitable for residential cooling or heating and domestic hot water production systems. A staggered heat exchanger has been installed and a commercial salt hydrate was tested. Such type of exchanger has not been tested for salt hydrates and in such a temperature range. Data were collected by applying three different HTF flow rates on the melting and solidification time of the salt hydrate.

EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP DESCRIPTION

Figure 1 show the test rig used in the experiments. An insulated heat storage glass tank is used that permits visual

observation and recording of the melting and solidification processes. Tank dimensions are: 600 x 120 x 100mm (Length x Width x Depth). A staggered type heat exchanger was immersed in the tank with technical characteristics given in Table 1. The heat exchanger is rotated by 90° so as to retain the height up to 50mm to minimize the phase separation issue (Figure 2). Hot water was supplied by an 80lt boiler with a 4kW electric heater and cold water was supplied by a 200lt water buffer tank connected to an air to water heat pump. The experimental rig also comprises a circulation pump (Grundfos® ALPHA 2 32-60 180 inverter pump), a three-way temperature control valve (Belimo® LR24A-SR valve and Vector® TCI-W11 controller), a flowmeter (rotameter with measuring range of 6-60lt/h with $\pm 4\%$ accuracy), thermocouples (T-type, with $\pm 0.5\%$ accuracy), and the necessary piping and valves to regulate water flow.

Figure 1 Lay out of the small experimental facility used in the experiments.

Table 1. Heat Exchanger Features

Number of tubes	12
Inner tube diameter (mm)	7.75
Outer tube diameter (mm)	9.525
Tube material	Copper
Fins material	Aluminium
Fin thickness (mm)	0.3
Fin length (mm)	68
Fin spacing (mm)	5.0

Data recording for PCM temperatures, HTF inlet/outlet temperatures, under charging/discharging processes, was accomplished by a data logger (National instrument® cDAQ - 9174 base, 2 x 9213 16ch cards, LabVIEW® data logger) and a personal computer. Thermal insulation has been applied on the outer side of the tank glass walls. The space between the tubes, the fins and the tank is filled with PCM. Hot HTF supplied from hot water boiler, delivers its thermal energy through HE and melts the PCM causing charging process. HTF inlet temperature is above the melting point of PCM in use. Charging is complete when PCM melts and an amount of HTF heat is now stored in the molten PCM. During the solidification (discharging) process, HTF supplied by the cold water buffer tank in a low temperature according to the PCM used. Cold HTF flows through the tube and solidifies the molten PCM absorbing the heat of the exothermic phase change. The stored energy is released from the PCM as it solidifies and discharges.

To analyse the heat exchanger thermal performance and the charging and discharging process taking place in the

Discharging: Cold water from the buffer tank circulates with a temperature of about 8°C less than the S44 melting temperature. Inlet temperature was controlled similarly with the charging process by a three-way mixing valve. The solidification process ends when the temperature of the thermocouples at the edges of the exchanger (Figure 2) is measured about 3°C or less than the nominal solidification temperature.

The experiments were performed by applying three HTF flow rates: 30lt/h, 45lt/h and 60lt/h.

REPRODUCIBILITY AND ERROR ANALYSIS

All the experiments were performed at least two times in order to assure the consistency of the results. Prior experience with the discussed system and with other storage systems has helped to achieve reproducibility of the results [20,21]. In Figure 3 it is presented an indicative plot of the inlet and outlet water temperatures for a HTF flow rate of 30 lt/hr. The results of two experiments, No 1 and 2, are similar for the entire charging and discharging procedure and this is also true for the temperature of the PCM. The same similarity yielded from the other experiments as well, so the reproducibility was validated.

Figure 3 Comparison of the inlet and outlet water temperatures for experiments No1 and No2 with 30 lt/hr flow rate.

The measurements of the temperature and the volumetric flow rate follow a rectangular distribution as each measurement has the same propability to be wherever between the range that the uncertainty defines. For the thermocouples, each measurement uncertainty derives from the combination of the accuracy of the sensors and the A/D converter as it is listed in Table 3. The temperature range that the thermocouples can measure is from -40 °C to 70 °C. For the flow meter, the measurement is obtained once (either 30, 45 or 60 lt/hr) and the sensor is analog.

Table 3 Accuracy of the temperature and flow rate sensors and A/D converter.

	Temperature, °C	Volumetric flow rate, lt/min
Sensor accuracy	$\pm (0.005 \cdot \text{Temp})$	$\pm (0.04 \cdot \text{Flow})$
Sensor reader accuracy	$\pm (0.15 + 0.002 \cdot \text{Temp})$	-
A/D Converter accuracy	$\pm (0.002 \cdot \text{Temp range})$	-

The maximum values of the relative errors for the water temperatures range between 1.23-1.28% for all the flow rates studied. The relative error for the volumetric flow rate is calculated 4.62%. The thermal power that the water provides (or extracts) to (from) the system and the environment is analogue to the difference of the inlet and the outlet temperature, as the flow rate and the heat capacity of the water are constant [21]. The calculated relative error for the heat power ranges between 0.24-0.38%.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Melting and solidification process of a material is related to the energy provided (charging) or extracted (discharging) by the HTF [20, 21]. In order to follow the operation of the TES unit the temperature difference between heat exchanger inlet and outlet was monitored and recorded. At the beginning of each experiment, the heat flow rate was maximised due to high temperature difference while it reduces as temperatures converge. Apart from flowrate, a key role regarding melting and solidification processes of a PCM is the temperature variation between HTF inlet temperature and PCM temperature.

The starting and ending points of each process were defined as follows: the start of charging is defined when the inlet temperature curve reaches its maximum for the first time since the beginning of the experiment. The end of charging is defined right before the sharp raise of the inlet temperature curve at the end of the charging process. The start of discharging is defined when the inlet temperature curve becomes horizontal. Finally, the end of discharging is defined at the last measurement of the experiment. Also, the mean charging and discharging inlet temperatures were calculated based on those start/end definitions. In Table 4 the mean temperature values and the duration of each process are given for the S44 experiments. Although, the average inlet temperatures are not exactly the same, it can be stated that the duration of charging or discharging is not a linear function of the water flow rate. Consequently, doubling the flow rate does not result to reducing the duration to the half although with high flow rates the flow becomes turbulent and the heat transfer is enhanced.

Table 4. Duration and mean inlet temperature for the S44 experiments.

	Charging			Discharging		
	30	45	60	30	45	60
Feed rate (lt/hr)						
Duration (hr)	3.39	3.10	2.75	4.55	2.95	2.44
Average inlet temperature (°C)	52.5	52.4	52.3	35.3	35.5	36.3

It is clear that for the low flow rate, the duration of the charging is significantly shorter than discharging. On the other hand, for the high flow rate the duration of charging is about half an hour larger than discharging. So, there is a trend the duration of discharging to be affected strongly by the feed rate. This effect may be attributed to the formation of solid PCM around the tubes which inhibits the heat transfer via convection between the liquid PCM and the fins and tubes. It must be pointed out that the conductivity of S44 is higher at the solid phase than the liquid (Table 2).

In Fig. 4 inlet and outlet water temperatures are plotted and it is clear that how charging or discharging times are reduced as

the water flow rate increases. Additionally, the phenomenon of subcooling is evident on the discharging outlet curves at the areas where they present a dip. Subcooling, is not desirable in a PCM as it prolongs the duration when the heat transfer occurs with sensible heat and not latent.

Figure 4 Water temperatures at the inlet and outlet of the tube for flow rates 30, 45 and 60 lt/hr.

In Fig. 5 the average PCM temperatures are depicted for the three feed rates applied. It is interesting that the subcooling characteristic dips in the temperature curves are not present in this diagram. However, the points where the slope of the discharging curves changes are clear for all curves. The points are located at (3.29hr, 41.4°C), (3.55hr, 41.7°C) and (4.05hr, 41.3°C) for 30, 45 and 60 lt/hr respectively (green dots on the diagram).

Figure 5 PCM temperatures for flow rates 30, 45 and 60 lt/hr.

In Figs. 7 and 8 the instant heat transfer rate between the water and the rest of the system (PCM, tubes, fins, losses) is calculated for the three flow rates. In both diagrams the 60 lt/hr case starts with the highest heat transfer rate and then reduces lower from the other two rates. In discharging, the subcooling effect is again obvious. Moreover, the accumulated energy was calculated which is equal to the area under the curves of the instant heat transfer.

Figure 7 Instant heat transfer for charging for flow rates 30, 45 and 60 lt/hr.

Figure 8 Instant heat transfer for discharging for flow rates 30, 45 and 60 lt/hr.

It is expected the accumulated energy to be equal for all the flow rates. As an example one can bring the case of the electric

battery whose capacity does not depend on the rate that it was charged. TES systems are the thermal analogue of the electric batteries. It must be stated also that part of the accumulated energy is lost the ambience due to the imperfect insulation of the tank. So, the values of the accumulated energies are listed in Table 5. For charging the values of the accumulated energies are similar, contrary to discharging where the values show differences. However, as the expanded uncertainty for the accumulated energies is higher such differences fall within the range of the calculated errors. Furthermore, as the losses inhibit the charging process it is expected that the accumulated energy will be higher for the charging process than the discharging, which is in accordance with the experimental results.

Table 5. Accumulated energies for charging and discharging for all feed rates.

Feed rate (lt/hr)	Charging			Discharging		
	30	45	60	30	45	60
Accumulated energy (kWh)	0.386	0.347	0.345	0.287	0.309	0.229

CONCLUSIONS

The performance of an LHTES unit using a staggered heat exchanger was studied using a commercial salt hydrate and considering the limitations for a low temperature solar application [21]. Three different HTF flow rates were applied and their influence on the melting and solidification time of the salt hydrate was evaluated. The LHTES unit studied can be considered as an effective solution with short response times up on charging. Discharging performance is strongly affected by the thermal transfer limitations as well as the super cooling of the salt hydrate. The latter may be addressed either by optimised TES operation control or heat exchanger design.

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